

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF A CONCENTRATING SOLAR COOKER UNDER HAZY WEATHER CONDITION

¹Dahiru, D. Y.; ¹Samaila, U.; and ²Habou, D.;

¹Mechanical Engineering Department, Federal University of Technology, P. M. B. 2076, Yola Adamawa State, Nigeria.

²Mechanical Engineering Programme, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University P.M.B. 0248 Bauchi, Bauchi State-Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Experimental performance evaluation of a concentrating solar energy cooker with mirrors glued on the inside wall of the parabolic concentrator as reflective material with reflectivity of over 80% is presented herein. Series of boiling water tests, cooking tests of rice and comparative analysis tests with other solar cookers were carried out in July and August 2002 at Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi under various levels of atmospheric turbidity. These yielded very encouraging and satisfactory results. The tracking of the cooker was done manually and thus has to be adjusted in every 15 minutes during cooking time. The cooker was able to boil 666g of water and cook 300g of rice in three hours under the test condition. Furthermore the comparative analysis test results with other solar cookers showed that the temperature of the present cooker was found to have reached 70°C in 45 min. The maximum temperature reached by parabolic box and flat plate single glaze solar cooker was 60°C in 2 hours 15 minutes and 2 hours 45 minutes respectively. While that of flat-plate double glaze and Sun Spot solar cooker was found to have reached 77°C in 2hrs 45minutes and 50°C in 30 minutes. The present cooker was able to cook rice and boil water with an overall utilization efficiency of 21.5%.

KEY WORDS: Solar Energy, Concentrating Cooker, Parabolic, Hazy

INTRODUCTION

Solar energy is a broad energy source and modern day engineering tends to find ways and capabilities of converting it into useful work for the society in an efficient, economic and environmentally friendly manner. For the development of indigenous science and technology in the world, a lot of work has been done by engineers and scientist (El Sebail and Ibrahim; (2005) in harnessing solar energy for both industrial and domestic use by designing various appliances or equipment for different purposes.

The heat energy produced by the sun is immense. In equatorial regions the solar radiation can exceed 1000 watts/m² (Petri; 1995). In a good sunlight, it is equivalent to half the power of an electric kettle. It only takes 10 – 15 Minutes to boil water on a solar cooker. And it's free, as long as you have dear blue skies. About 2 billion people, which represents one-third of the population of the world, are daily dependent on firewood as the source of their domestic cooking and heating energy. They live in the tropics, which is the most favourable area for the use of solar energy. Petri 1995 reported that every year the cutting of firewood results in the loss of 20,000 – 25,000 km² of tropical forest.

Nigeria which lies in the tropics (Latitude 4^o16' and 13^o52'N) and is endowed with abundant sunshine all the year round with daily sunshine hours in the southern part averaging about 8 hours during dry season and about 4 hours during the wet months. Higher values of daily sunshine hours are obtainable in the northern part of the country, averaging about 10 hours during dry season and 6 hours during the wet months (Pelemo *et al*; 2002). The period from November to April usually known as the dry season, is marked by a prevailing north- easterly wind regime known locally as the harmattan. The harmattan is a dry but cool dust – laden wind blowing from the subtropical anticyclone across the equatorial trough in West Africa. The wet

season in the northern part of Nigeria is the period from May to October when 80% or more of mean annual rainfall is received (Pelemo *et al*; 2002). However, the maximum mean monthly rainfall and the highest number of rain occur in the months of July and September as reported by Ayodele; 1987 (The testing period of this cooker).

Both rural and urban population in Nigeria follow an income based cooking energy ladder starting from fuel wood and ending at liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) and electricity. Since a significant portion of cooking energy is required at low temperatures, solar cookers in general and parabolic solar cooker (PSC) in particular offer an alternative solution for supplementing such thermal energy requirements. Nigeria is an ideal location for disseminating renewable energy technologies (Musa *et al*; 1991).

The re-emergence of interest in solar energy utilization started in the early 1970s due to the then rising cost of energy from conventional sources. Solar energy is the world's most abundant source of energy. The amount of solar energy received by the surface of the earth per minutes is greater than the energy utilization by the entire population in one year (Burari and Sambo; 2003). Solar energy being available every where is attractive for stand alone system, particularly in the rural parts of the developing nations such as Nigeria, where the greater percentage of the people dwell.

A large number of solar cookers have been developed in many countries. These cookers are broadly divided into direct or focusing type (PSC), indirect or box type (El-Sebaili and Ibrahim; 2005), and advanced cookers, the problem of cooking out doors is avoided to some extent. Using phase change materials as storage media inside solar cookers has solve the problem of cooking in the evening or during low intensity solar radiation periods. Some Nigerian institutions and research centres have conducted a number of researches and development activities in different types of solar cookers (Musa *et al*; 1991). These include solar clay hotbox, solar concrete hotbox, and all sides reflecting booster solar cookers. Others are frame reflector, oil storage type, global cooker and mirror dish concentrating type of cooker. As a result of activities conducted in solar cookers, papers on different types of solar cookers have been presented at the annual conference of the Solar Energy Society of Nigeria.

The aim of this work is to evaluate the performance of a concentrating solar cooker under hazy weather condition which has previously been designed and constructed (Dahiru *et al*; 2007).

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Testing Procedure of the Solar Cooker

After the fabrication of the solar cooker experimental tests were conducted in order to determine its function ability. The tests were conducted in the months of July and August 2002. This period was characterized by hazy solar radiation because of rainfalls and cloud covers. An average size cooking pot (absorber), coated black on the outside, was placed at the focal point of the cooker and the whole arrangement was placed under the sun. The mechanical manual tracking mechanism was used to get maximum concentration of the solar radiation at the focus. A known quantity of water was poured into the cooking pot. The temperatures of the absorber surface T_r , water T_w , reflector T_R , and ambient T_∞ , wind speed W_s and solar radiation I_g were noted and recorded at 15 minutes intervals.

Experiments were also conducted under the same ambient condition with other solar cookers to study the effect of hazy weather on cooking performance. The results of the experiments are as shown in Tables 1- 4. The experiments commenced at about 9:00 a.m. and were continued until maximum temperature of the cooking fluid was achieved.

Test Instrumentation

During all the experiments, the solar radiation intensity on a parabolic surface was measured using plint model solarimeter calibrated as 100mv/kwm². Type K thermocouples and kane-may KM 330 digital temperature output instruments were employed for the accurate measurement of the temperatures of the ambient, reflector, absorber and fluid/ food subjected to heat. The thermocouples were the 2mm diameter

stainless steel, grounded junction type; they have accuracy of $\pm 0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Cup Counter anemometer was employed for determining wind speed. Its accuracy was about $\pm 1\%$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results obtained from the experiment are shown in Tables1- 4 and Figures 1-4.

Three forms of tests were conducted. The boiling water test, the cooking test of rice and the comparative analysis with other types of solar cookers test.

Six different parameters were measured during the experimental tests. The Absorber temperatures, Reflector temperature, ambient temperature, Food/fluid temperature were measured using the k – type

thermocouples. The global solar radiation data were obtained using the solarimeter. Then the wind speed data were collected with the cup counter anemometer.

Boiling Test of Water: Table 1 shows the boiling test of water. The maximum temperature attained by the water was 91°C at 11:25 a.m. with an average solar radiation of 519.5w/m². The graphical representation of

this test is shown on Figure 1a. As can be seen from the graph the highest temperature was reached between 10: 40 a.m. and 11: 25 a.m. due to very low wind speed recorded in the morning on that day. Figure 1b showed the temperature plotted against the global radiation which was obtained from Table 1. From the graph it can be deduced that the high temperature recorded was at an average global radiation of 605- 610 w/m² which is similar to that of Figure 1. On this figure it can be seen that temperature fluctuates even at higher global radiation, this was due to intermittent cloud covers and wind effect.

Cooking Test of Rice: Table 2, shows the cooking test of 0.3kg of rice, even though the weather condition was partially cloudy, the rice was completely cooked at 11:40 a.m. after attaining temperature of 89°C, with an average global solar radiation of 475.4w/m². The cooking time was exactly 3 hours. This is shown graphically on Figure 2 with temperature plotted against time of the day. The temperature reaches its peaks at 11: 10 a.m. after which it decline due partly to convective heat losses intermittent cloud covers and higher magnitude of diffuse radiation. Another cooking test was conducted in the afternoon of the same day; the rice was cooked at 4:05 p.m. This was characterized by intermittent cloud cover. The maximum temperature attained for this experiments was 72°C at 1: 50 p.m. with an average global solar radiation of 639.2w/m² as shown on Table 3 and graphical representation on Figure 3 which is the graph of temperature plotted against global radiation to enable a smooth comparison with that of Figure 1b as shown on the graph the highest temperature was reached at an average global radiation of 640 W/m² which is slightly

higher due to very low wind speed recorded that period. Fluctuations can be deduced from the graph as a result of intermittent cloud covers.

Time of the day	Absorber Tempt. $T_a(^{\circ}\text{C})$	Water Tempt. $T_w(^{\circ}\text{C})$	Reflector Tempt. $T_R(^{\circ}\text{C})$	Ambient Tempt. $T_{\infty} (^{\circ}\text{C})$	Global Radiation $I_g(\text{W}/\text{m}^2)$	Wind Speed $W_s(\text{m}/\text{s})$
9:10	30	28	33	32	486	0.1
9:25	42	37	33	31	291	0.1
9:40	40	42	33	30	354	0.2
9:55	56	59	33	31	505	0.3
10:10	59	75	34	31	518	0.1
10:25	59	81	40	32	565	0.3
10:40	75	85	35	32	596	0.3
10:55	80	89	37	33	610	0.2
11:10	76	90	42	34	613	0.3
11:25	81	91	41	34	657	2
11:40	69	80	38	32	328	3
11:55	43.8	78	35	33	243	5

Comparative Analysis Test: Tables 4 shows the comparative analysis of the present solar cooker with parabolic Box type solar cooker, flat plate single glaze, flat plate double glaze and Sun-Spot (Solar cooker trade name) solar cooker tested under the same weather condition. Although the present cooker makes use of direct beam radiation only, unlike other cookers which make use of both direct and diffuse radiations. The temperature of the present cooker was found to have reached 70°C in 45 min. The maximum temperature reached by parabolic box and flat plate single glaze solar cooker was 60°C in 2hours 15 minutes and 2hours 45 minutes. While that of flat-plate double glaze and Sun Spot solar cooker was found

Table1: Temperature Distribution for Boiling Test of Water

Weather Condition: Clear, Setting time: 9:10 a.m., Date: 26/06/2002, Mass of water: 666g

to have reached 77°C in 2hrs 45mins and 50°C in 30 minutes. This is shown graphically on Figure 4 with water temperature plotted against time of the day. It can be deduced that increase in the absorber temperature invariably increases the food/water temperature. From the graph it can be seen that the present cooker recorded higher performance when suddenly it went on fluctuating which was due to convective heat loss and cloudy weather condition. The other reason for this is the increase in the level of diffuse radiation due to atmospheric water particles. This of course lowers the magnitude of beam radiation utilized by the present cooker.

CONCLUSION

Solar radiation can be effectively and efficiently utilized for cooking in our homes if proper design is used and certain procedures can be followed. A major factor for effective use is the proper selection of time of cooking and proper focusing of the reflected rays to the focal spot region. Rice was cooked using the present cooker even though the time taken was a little bit longer when compared with conventional kerosene, gas, fire wood and electric cookers. This is attributed to natural phenomena of cloud interception and rain falls. This cooker will perform better during sunny days by using only the beam component of

solar radiation. It is believed that shorter boiling time and consequently higher efficiency would be achieved during dry season dear blue sky condition.

The three tests conducted were the boiling water test, cooking test of 300g of rice and comparative analysis test with other solar cookers. The cooker was able to boiled 666g of water, cooked 300g of rice in 3hours under this hazy weather condition. Furthermore the comparative analysis test results with other solar cookers showed that the temperature of the present cooker was found to have reached 70°C in 45 min. The maximum temperature reached by parabolic box and flat plate single glaze solar cooker was 60°C in 2 hours 15 minutes and 2 hours 45 minutes. While that of flat-plate double glaze and Sun Spot solar cooker was found to have reached 77°C in 2hrs 45minutes and 50°C in 30 minutes.

Table 2: Temperature Distribution for Cooking Test of 300g of Rice

Time of the day	Absorber Tempt. $T_r(^{\circ}C)$	Water/Food Tempt. $T_f(^{\circ}C)$	Reflector Tempt. $T_R(^{\circ}C)$	Ambient Tempt. $T_{\infty}(^{\circ}C)$	Global Radiation $I_g(W/m^2)$	Wind Speed $W_s(m/s)$
8:40	31	25	30	28	381	0.1
8:55	53	32	30	28	426	0.1
9:10	79	40	31	29	450	0.1
9:25	80	50	33	28	477	0.1
9:40	74	63	35	29	506	0.2
9:55	74	74	35	31	518	0.1
10:10	71	77	36	30	537	0.2
10:25	66	77	36	30	557	0.3
10:40	88	78	38	30	575	0.1
10:55	91	80	39	30	585	0.2
11:10	73	89	40	31	614	0.2
11:25	60	80	40	32	604	0.4
11:40	66	86	41	32	620	0.3
11:55	69	84	36	32	627	0.2
12:10	65	79	40	31	638	0.5
12:25	65	81	40	33	639	0.2

Weather condition: Partially clear, Setting time: 8:40 AM, Date: 02/07/2002, Mass of water: 999g, Mass of rice : 300g

REFERENCES

Ayodele S. C. (1987); Energy Development and Utilization in Nigeria, Nigerian institute of social and economic research, Ibadan (Bulleting News Letter).

Burari, F.W. and Sambo, A.S. (2003), Analysis of Monthly average daily global solar radiation for Bauchi, Nigerian Journal of Tropical Engineering Vol. 4 Nos. 1&2.

Dahiru, D.Y., Malachy, S. and Asere, A.A. (2007), The development of a concentrating solar energy cooker under hazy weather condition, Journal of Research in Engineering (Accepted for publication).

El-Sebaili, A.A. and Ibrahim, A. (2005), Experimental testing of a box type solar cooker using the standard procedure of cooking power, Renewable Energy journal Vol. 30, Nos 1861-1871.

Table 3: Temperature Distribution for Cooking Test of 300g of Rice under Cloudy Condition.

Time of the day	Absorber Tempt. $T_f(^{\circ}\text{C})$	Water/Food Tempt. $T_f(^{\circ}\text{C})$	Reflector Tempt. $T_R(^{\circ}\text{C})$	Ambient Tempt. $T_{\infty}(^{\circ}\text{C})$	Global Radiation I_g (W/m^2)	Wind Speed W_s (m/s)
12:35	55	29	40	37	639	0.2
12:50	47	48	36	33	646	0.1
1:05	59	56	42	34	640	0.1
1:20	56	63	39	32	632	0.3
1:35	50	68	41	33	633	0.2
1:50	70	72	41	34	645	0.1
2:05	57	63	38	33	640	0.3
2:20	74	69	40	32	604	0.2
2:35	53	69	35	32	89	0.2
2:50	62	68	42	36	663	0.1
3:05	46	64	39	33	239	0.4
3:20	43	57	37	33	215	1.2
3:35	46	55	38	34	319	1.2
3:50	53	56	39	33	552	2
4:05	35	54	35	32	117	2

Weather Condition: Cloudy, Setting Time: 12:35 p.m., Date: 02/07/2002, Mass of Water: 999g
Mass of Rice: 300g

Musa, U. Sambo, A. S. and Bala, E. J. (1991) Design, Construction and Performance of a parabolic concentrator cooker, Nigerian Journal of Solar Energy, Vol.10,pp.19- 25.

Pelemo, D. A., Fassi, M. K., Owolabi, S. A., and Shaniyi, J. A.; (2002); Effective utilization of solar energy for cooking, Nigerian Journal of Engineering Management, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp 13 – 18.

Petri, K. (1995) Solar Cookers for use in Namibia; Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Helsinki University of Technology.

Received for Publication: 16/05/2007

Accepted for Publication: 15/08/2007

Corresponding Author:

Dahiru, D. Y.;

Mechanical Engineering Department, Federal University of Technology, P. M. B. 2076, Yola Adamawa State. Nigeria.

Email: dahirudasin@yahoo.com, +2348025508154;